

Resemblance Study of Machine Learning Techniques to Predict Heart Disease Using WEKA Tool

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Abstract—Coronary heart sickness is highlighted because the predominant one most of the diverse death elements. Detecting coronary heart disease tends to be a bit complex because of inadequate expertise and enjoy of the clinical practitioners concerning warning symptoms of coronary heart failure. By means of adopting the nice suitable records mining strategies, early detection of heart-associated illnesses may be finished and also preventing it from taking place. Each the device mastering (ML) and records Mining (DM) strategies show to be powerful and good sized inside the domain of the medical enterprise. Currently, a lot of methods have been implemented for prediction analysis. Various ranges concerned within the proposed approach are a group of dataset, education, and testing, collection of user signs and symptoms. This paper is a comparison of the output of various machine learning techniques like OneR, J48, and Random Forest on heart disease dataset in order to determine which algorithm is best for predicting heart disease correctly and is done in terms of some parameters inclusive of accuracy, error reputation charge and execution time.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Heart Disease, OneR, J48, Random Forest, Weka, Accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a type of data analysis that automates the creation of analytical models. It's a field of artificial intelligence based on the premise that computers can learn from data, recognize patterns, and make decisions with minimal human intervention. This study aims to find best algorithm to predict heart

disease dataset based on different features using the different techniques of Machine Learning (ML).

According to today's imbalanced way of life, the human coronary heart is liable to crucial sort of sicknesses. It's ensuing in vital illnesses and troubles bobbing up due to diabetes, stress, and severe smoking. These kinds of factors seriously have an effect on the human heart and cause a diffusion of coronary heart illnesses[1]. The essential reason for heart disorder is blockage in coronary arteries, which specially supplies blood to the coronary heart. As a result, this can cause lifestyles-threatening troubles, from time to time loss of life. The early those signs and symptoms are detected, the extra are the chances for set off remedy and saving a human lifestyles[2].

So, it is important to predict the chances and prevent heart diseases. The numerous epidemic illnesses may be firstly examined, identified, managed, tested and avoided using predictive analysis and early detection mechanisms of diverse data mining techniques [4]. The vast information set can be certainly processed thru the records analysis methods the usage of various algorithms. The desired and helpful sample is processed to be able to correctly forecast and expect the outcome.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Radhanath Patra¹, Bonomali Khuntia¹, uses the numerous techniques, processes which have used to teach the version of coronary coronary heart datasets together with feature desire, numpy, pandas library, preference tree classifier, KNN classifier, entropy,

gini- index, confusion matrix. The result indicates that selection tree classifier is handiest and appropriate for prediction of UCI repository Cleveland heart dataset.

Ramya G. Franklin², B. Muthukumar² uses the CNN, LSTM is being proposed for coronary heart sickness identity and prediction which yields in improvised output than the relaxation of the prevailing strategies. Numerous stages worried within the proposed approach are a set of dataset, schooling, and checking out, series of consumer signs, securely forwarding the records with the aid of utilising AES, and subsequently, result is being generated in PDF format. Comparative overall performance in datasets concerning medicine is followed in predicting coronary heart sickness strategies in comparison to the rest of other ML techniques.

Mohini Chakarverti³, Saumya Yadhav³, Rajiv Rajan³ uses the facts that suite accommodates overall seventy six capabilities. But, entire assessments require a subset of 14 functions. In particular, Cleveland database particularly is used by the gadget studying researchers throughout the assessments. A contrast between proposed study and in advance method (the usage of arithmetic imply) is carried out in terms of sure parameters such as accuracy, errors reputation charge and execution time.

III. METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to classify Heart Disease dataset into two categories (presence and absence) using machine learning techniques [1]. This section offers the classification technique used to are expecting heart sickness based at the behavioural features[3]. The technique involves 3 important stages, which might be accumulating dataset, pre- processing and category as shown in Figure 1.

A. WEKA

It is an open source software that includes tools for data pre-processing, machine learning algorithm implementation, and visualization tools, allowing you to create device studying techniques and observe them to real-world facts mining techniques [4]. WEKA implements a number of algorithms in

Each of these categories. You can choose an algorithm and set the desired parameters and run it on the dataset[4]. Then, WEKA could give you the statistical output of the model processing. The diverse models can be implemented on the identical dataset [4]. You can then examine the outputs of different models and choose the exceptional that meets your cause. As a consequence, the use of WEKA results in a faster improvement of dataset studying fashions at the whole [4].

B. Collecting Dataset

A number of variables are used to classify whether a person has chance for presence of heart disease or not. The dataset used in this study comes from the Kaggle repository, and it contains 270 instances of heart disease with 14 attributes and a known target class. This data set is used as training data for the classifier. Information of the variables that have been used within the facts as proven in Figure I [3].

Figure1: Methodology for Heart Disease Classification

C. Pre-Processing

In Data Mining pre-processing is a crucial stage. It deals with entries that are missing, incomplete, or invalid for a variety of reasons, including data entry errors. In addition, there are also attributes that are not relevant to the studies in facts mining [3]. The beside the point information consisting of id ought to also be removed from the dataset because its presence can lessen the pleasant or accuracy of the records mining category test [3]. The dataset for this study is made up of nominal values. Those facts ought to be was numerical values, which means the nominal values

have to be transformed into numerical values[3].By using remodeling the nominal into numerical values, the statistics at the moment are able to feed into classification set of rules[3].

D. Classification Experiment

The category experiment is executed the usage of Waikato environment for information evaluation (WEKA).In this paper, we will use different machine learning algorithms and techniques for across multiple classification methods so that results can be compared [3]. In this work, the evaluation metrics used includes the classification accuracy and time taken to build the model.

E. Evaluation Matrix

An evaluation matrix is vital for evaluating the outcomes of a category test [3]. The goal is to create an unmarried size that can be used across multiple category techniques in order that consequences may be compared[3]. On this paintings, the assessment metrics used includes the classification accuracy, coefficient metric, and time taken to build the version.

1	age in years
2	sex(1=male,0=female)
3	chest pain type resting blood pressure
4	serum
5	cholesterol
6	fasting blood sugar
7	resting electrocardiographic result
8	maximum heart rate achieved
9	exercise included angina(exhang)
10	old peak
11	slope
12	number of major vessels
13	thal
14	num(target)

Table 1: Features of the Heart Disease Dataset

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

In this study, we will use different machine learning algorithms and techniques for Heart Disease Prediction and are listed below:

A. Classification Algorithms

J48 Algorithm: It is a decision tree technique and is one the most popular classification techniques in machine learning, where it used in decision support. It permits you to predict the goal variable of a new dataset record [5].

Through mastering simple choice regulations inferred from beyond data, the cause of employing a j48 is to increase an education version that may be used to predict the class or price of the target variable (training records)[5]. We begin from the foundation of the tree when the usage of decision trees to predict a class label for a file. The values of the basis characteristic and the report's characteristic are compared.

Correctly Classified Instances	207	76.6667 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances	63	23.3333 %
Kappa statistic	0.5271	
Mean absolute error	0.274	
Root mean squared error	0.4601	
Relative absolute error	55.4778 %	
Root relative squared error	92.5962 %	
Total Number of Instances	270	

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

	TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	RDC Area	PRC Area	Class
	0.733	0.207	0.739	0.733	0.736	0.527	0.744	0.641	Presence
	0.793	0.267	0.788	0.793	0.791	0.527	0.744	0.737	Absence
Weighted Avg.	0.767	0.240	0.766	0.767	0.767	0.527	0.744	0.694	

=== Confusion Matrix ===

a	b	<- classified as
88	32	a = Presence
31	119	b = Absence

Figure2: Classification Accuracy by J48

Random Forest: It is a decision tree classification and regression extension of bagging. The "forest it builds, is an ensemble of selection bushes, usually trained with the "bagging" method.

The general concept of the bagging technique is that an aggregate of gaining knowledge of models increases the overall end result[6]. Bagged decision trees have the disadvantage of being built using a greedy algorithm that selects the best split point at each stage of the tree-building process[5].

Correctly Classified Instances	222	82.2222 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances	48	17.7778 %
Kappa statistic	0.6388	
Mean absolute error	0.2744	
Root mean squared error	0.3618	
Relative absolute error	55.5693 %	
Root relative squared error	72.8191 %	
Total Number of Instances	270	

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

	TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
	0.783	0.147	0.810	0.783	0.797	0.639	0.891	0.874	Presence
	0.853	0.217	0.831	0.853	0.842	0.639	0.891	0.896	Absence
Weighted Avg.	0.822	0.186	0.822	0.822	0.822	0.639	0.891	0.886	

=== Confusion Matrix ===

a	b	<- classified as
94	26	a = Presence
22	128	b = Absence

Figure2: Classification Accuracy by Random Forest

OneR: OneR classifier is one of the most simple and successful classifier algorithms for machine learning classification problem. It creates one rule for each predictor in the data, then chooses the rule with the smallest overall error to be its single rule. The set of rules starts off evolved by means of iterating over every value of every function. For that value, count the wide

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variety of samples from each class that has that characteristic fee. Report the maximum common class of the feature fee, and the error of that prediction.

Correctly Classified Instances	196	72.5926 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances	74	27.4074 %
Kappa statistic	0.445	
Mean absolute error	0.2741	
Root mean squared error	0.5235	
Relative absolute error	55.4943 %	
Root relative squared error	105.3565 %	
Total Number of Instances	270	

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

	TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
	0.692	0.247	0.692	0.692	0.692	0.445	0.723	0.615	Presence
	0.753	0.308	0.753	0.753	0.753	0.445	0.723	0.705	Absence
Weighted Avg.	0.726	0.281	0.726	0.726	0.726	0.445	0.722	0.665	

=== Confusion Matrix ===

a	b	<- classified as
83	37	a = Presence
37	113	b = Absence

Figure4: Classification Accuracy by OneR

V. RESULT

The classification of this dataset was done to prediction between presence and absence of heart disease based on the behavioural characteristics. The dataset had a total of 14 nominal attributes (features). Result of the testing using evaluation on the training dataset indicate that Random Forest has 82.2% accuracy level, J48 has 76.6% accuracy level and OneR has 72.5% accuracy. However, the Random

Forest method is faster than J48 and in terms of processing speed. Below Table 1 shows the performance comparison chart of three algorithms on heart disease dataset.

ML Techniques	Accuracy	Time Taken to Build a Model
Random Forest	82%	0.03s
J48 Algorithm	76.60%	0.02s
OneR	72.50%	0.25s

Table 1: Performance Comparison Chart

VI. CONCLUSION

Heart Disease Prediction helps in prevention and early detection. Through the predictive analysis and early detection mechanism of various facts mining technique, the diverse epidemic sicknesses may be to start with analyzed, diagnosed, controlled and avoided. This paper offered the method and consequences for coronary heart sickness category experiment based on their behavioural features. This comparison study has given us a better understanding of how the various machine learning models work and how they perform in real-world scenarios.

The end result suggests that Random Forest technique holds correct for the evaluation of scientific records class mainly for heart illnesses than J48 Algorithm and OneR.

VII. FUTURE WORK

In data mining, we know that as the size of training dataset increases, the performance of the created model would be enhanced. As a future work, we can also include other attributes like person with other diseases like diabetes, genetically chance for heart disease (history of family members have heart diseases) etc and more records that are collected as part of research and apply different machine learning techniques on the new dataset. This will result in improving the model accuracy of the test.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Radhanath Patra, Bonomali Khuntia "Predictive Analysis of Rapid Spread of Heart Disease with Data Mining"
- [2] Ramya G. Franklin, B. Muthukumar "Survey of Heart Disease Prediction and Identification using Machine Learning"
- [3] Mohini Chakarverti, Saumya Yadhav, Rajiv Rajan "Classification Technique for Heart Disease Prediction in Data Mining"
- [4] https://www.tutorialspoint.com/weka/what_is_weka.htm
- [5] N. Bhargava and G. Sharma, "Decision Tree Analysis on J48 Algorithm for Data Mining"
- [6] <https://builtin.com/data-science/random-forest-algorithm>.